

Event Abstract

Mitigation of the Toxic Effects of Periodontal Pathogens by Candidate Probiotics in an Invertebrate Model

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Background: The larvae of the waxmoth *Galleria mellonella* was used to investigate the protective activity of the candidate oral probiotics *Lactobacillus rhamnosus* GG (LHR), *Lactobacillus reuteri* (LR) and *Streptococcus salivarius* K-12 (SS) against the periodontal pathogens *Fusobacterium nucleatum* (FN), *Porphyromonas gingivalis* (PG) and *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* (AA).

Method: Probiotics were delivered to the larvae (i) concomitantly with the pathogen in the same larval pro-leg; (ii) concomitantly with the pathogen in different pro-legs and (iii) prior to inoculation with the pathogen in different pro-legs.

Results: The periodontal pathogens killed at least 50% of larvae within 24 h although PG and FN were significantly more virulent than AA in the order FN>PG>AA ($p < 0.05$). The candidate probiotics however were not lethal to the larvae at doses up to 10^7 cells/larvae. Wax worm survival rates increased up to 60% for some probiotic/pathogen combinations compared with control larvae inoculated with pathogens only ($p \leq 0.01$). SS was the most effective probiotic against FN challenge and LHR the least, in simultaneous administration and in pre-treatment, SS and LR were generally the most protective against all pathogens (up to 60% survival) *P. gingivalis*-LR>LHR>SS and for *A. actinomycetemcomitans* SS>LHR and LR.

Conclusion: In summary, the periodontal pathogens were variably lethal to *G. mellonella* and the candidate probiotics had measurable protective effects, which were greatest when administered simultaneously with the periodontal pathogens, suggesting protective

effects based on bacterial interaction, and providing a basis for mechanistic studies.

Keywords: Periodontal pathogens; *Galleria mellonella*; probiotics; infection model.

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